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Investigating the impacts of infrastructure on foreign direct investment in flow to Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study's primary objective is to empirically investigate the impacts of infrastructure on foreign direct investment inflow to Nigeria from 1996 to 2018. Specifically, it seeks to determine if there exists a long run relationship between infrastructure and FDI inflow in Nigeria or if these two macroeconomic variables converge in the long run. The understanding of the determinants of foreign direct investment (FDI) is an important issue of economy literature because of increasing investment requirements of the economies. Infrastructure has a vital role for economic development through promoting productivity, costs and trade. In this regard, the purpose of this paper is to investigate the impact of infrastructure of a country on foreign direct investment (FDI) level in that particular country by using five infrastructure indicators, including mobile cellular subscribers, railways rail lines, air transport and seaport infrastructure, by using Ordinary Least Square models with data covering the 1996-2018 period. The Eclectic Paradigm formed the theoretical background of this research with emphasis on the Location advantage of the OLI framework which pinpoints the role of infrastructure in attracting FDI. The results indicate that only two infrastructure variables, mobile cellular subscribers and seaport infrastructure quality causes an increases in FDI inflows. A close analysis of the results generally highlight the fact that Nigeria though a big market of about 200 million people and rich in resources, such as crude oil and natural gas, is still lagging behind its peers in terms of infrastructure and this has made it difficult for foreign investors to come into the country to invest as expected. Power Infrastructure, which has recurring transmission and distribution challenges, and Rail infrastructure, which has very low spread across the country in particular, showed poor results and considering the role of these two sub-sectors in the growth of any economy it becomes imperative that they must be resuscitated urgently to ensure that Nigeria can gain more inflow of Foreign Direct Investment.

Keywords

Nigeria, FDI, Infrastructure, foreign direct investment

Introduction

Developing infrastructure is a key issue in the development of any nation. This is because not only that it makes life easier by adding to the quality of life people live but also because it enables seamless performance of business/economic activities, which further increase the peoples living standard. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is one factor that adds to the amount of economic activities that enable economic growth and development. FDI is one of the three forms of international capital flows: the others are *portfolio investment*

and other such as bank loans. Many studies have identified infrastructure as the major of source of FDI inflow. Chakrabarti et al (2012) discovered a positive relationship between infrastructure and FDI inflow. Also, Omezzine (2011), and Hakro (2011) discovered that governance infrastructure affects FDI flows significantly. The availability of infrastructure promotes FDI because it reduces operational costs. Seetanah (2009) claimed that gains resulting from infrastructural development are closely linked with greater accessibility and a decrease in the cost of transportation. He further argued that the availability of public goods reduces a foreign company's cost of doing business thereby increasing its returns or profit significantly. Also, Erenberg (1993) asserts that domestic and multinational companies will operate with less efficiency and below their optimal level should public infrastructures not be extended to them because they would have to incur an additional cost of building infrastructures of their own and this will lead to duplication and wastage of the available scarce resources. Infrastructure development in the national space provides the enabling environment for such investments and to a great extent contributes to the safety of such investment.

The scarcity of infrastructure in Nigeria and Africa as a whole is a serious matter hindering the development of the African continent in general and Nigeria in particular. One of the most important and arguable the most challenging of the infrastructure gap in Nigeria is power or electricity. Electricity drives development and the amount of electricity supply in Nigeria hardly carries domestic needs not to talk of industrial and commercial needs. The various self-help employments such as hair dressing, welding, fashion and designing, to mention a few suffer greatly from inadequate power supply. If this is the fate of micro and small businesses, one would imagine what the big enterprises, especially manufacturing concerns pass through in the face of power problem in the country. Besides the issue of power are other vital infrastructure such as effective communication (including internet broadband), transportation (roads are only recently getting better and railways that have been moribund for decades are just coming back to life). Another critical infrastructure deficit is in the area of area of ports development. The Tincan Island and Apapa ports are simply inadequate to carry the demands of a highly import-dependent and export aspiring economy like Nigeria. The dredging of Calabar port and the envisaged development of deep sea port in Lagos and Delta states with the attendant easing of ports congestion, are however good omen). The low level of infrastructure development in the country, we speculate, is a developmental challenge and a factor in deterring investors.

Researches show that the flow of FDI to Africa is less than that going to other individual parts of the globe: Africa's share of global FDI inflows declined from 9.5 per cent in 1970 to 5.3 per cent in 2009. FDI flows in the world have increased dramatically from \$ 13.3 billion in 1970 to \$ 2.1 trillion in 2007 before declining to \$1.1 trillion in 2009 due to the global financial crisis in 2008-2009. However, Africa, as a region, has not benefited from the FDI boom since the volume of FDI inflows to the continent is not only low as a share of global FDI but is also on a downward trend for the last three decades as the above figures show (Denisia, 2010, Sichei & Kinyondo, 2012). They observe that FDI inflows to Africa have been to countries that are classified by the World Bank as oil and mineral dependent including South Africa, Angola, Nigeria, Equatorial Guinea, and Egypt, among others.

This phenomenon raises the questions as to whether Africa has been attracting one (asset- or resource-seeking) form of FDI or not. FDI to Africa has been attracted to countries endowed with natural resources. 10 leading recipients of FDI inflows in 2009 (Angola, Egypt, Nigeria, South Africa, Sudan, Algeria, Libya, Congo, Tunisia, Ghana and Equatorial Guinea) have large mineral and petroleum reserves and accounted for close to 75 per cent of annual FDI flows to Africa. It is our opinion that in addition to political and social instability this scenario can be, to a great extent, attributed to the fact that Africa, and Sub-Saharan Africa in particular, has less developed infrastructure. The reason is obvious: *any investor would like to invest in an environment with critical infrastructure that would promote business operations*. Denisia (2010) agrees much with this by observing that well established and quality infrastructure is an important determinant of FDI inflows.

This research will be significant to the following stakeholders within the Nigerian Economic system:

Government: It is expected that the recommendations of this work would be useful to policy makers in understanding the role of infrastructural investments and further draft policies that will improve the nexus of infrastructure, FDI inflows and economic growth.

Investors: Investors in the Nigeria economy can benefit from this research by getting a clearer picture of the depth of infrastructure situation in Nigeria with a view to better structuring their investment plans and portfolio.

Researchers: This research will also provide more in-depth quantitative information to researchers about existing infrastructural challenges and on going reforms with a view towards further research on the subject matter.

Research Problems

The acceleration of economic development is enhanced by the quantum of infrastructure available, which promote activities that enlarge the economy of any nation. Equally, in today's world no nation can develop as a closed system that is not allowing the inflow of resources from outside. This is why the contribution of foreign direct investment in accelerating development especially in a developing country can hardly be overstressed.

In Africa, and in particular the sub-Saharan Africa, there is a general low level of infrastructure development, and from our introductory background we have surmised that this scenario might be one of the reasons Africa's share of Direct Foreign Investment (FDI) is very low. Consequently, it is affirmed here that this might be contributing in slowing down the economic development of the African continent as a whole and Nigeria in particular. Nigeria as a nation has found out that the low level of infrastructure development is hindering her development and the ability to occupy her place among the committee of nations, despite being the largest economy in Africa. Nigeria, having about 27 percent of Africa's GDP and 76 percent of GDP of the West African sub-region, holds a lot of potential to unlock Africa's development. This cannot happen without adequate infrastructure, including credit market as mentioned by Blonigen & Piger (2011) and the inflow of appropriate level of foreign capital. Though there are other several factors determining the flow of foreign direct investment, but this study tries to x-ray the place of infrastructure in attracting foreign direct investment.

This part will include explanations of methods of data collection and analysis. The research methodology basically describes actions to be taken to investigate a research problem and the rationale for the application of specific procedures or techniques used to identify, process and analyze information and ultimately allowing the reader to critically evaluate a study's overall validity and reliability.

Quantitative research technique based on ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. Simon and Goes (2013) sees ex post facto research as one which is based on a fact or event that has already happened and at the same time employs the investigation and basic logic of enquiry like the experimental method.

As for this work, there are two key reasons for the choice of the ex post facto method. Firstly, the data is secondary and is collected from the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics, Central Bank of Nigeria, The International Civil Aviation Organization, World Economic Forum, National Electricity Regulation Commission, and World Bank. and other international database sources. The data-set will capture already computed and reported macroeconomic variables. Secondly, the reported figures for the variables of interest are not susceptible to our manipulations because they are information in public domain and are easily verifiable. Data-set will range from the period of 1996 to 2018

Description and Justification of Variables

Since this research focuses on impact of infrastructure on Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Nigeria, the key infrastructure sectors of the economy Transport, Power and Communications Infrastructures will be analyzed within a regression model aimed at assessing the effects on these sectors contribution towards attracting Foreign Direct Investment in Nigeria which will be proxied by **Foreign direct investment, net inflows**, while the explanatory variables of infrastructure established from the literature to have some desired effect on Foreign Direct Investment will include:

(1) **Power Infrastructure Quality-PIQ** - Which proxies Electric Power Consumption (Kwh per capita). Electric power consumption measures the production of power plants and combined heat and power plants less transmission, distribution, and transformation losses and own use by heat and power plants. An economy's production and consumption of electricity are basic indicators of its size and level of development.

Justification : Electricity is the backbone of the economic activities in any economy. Factories, Offices, Hospitals, Homes, Schools and other components of the economy need to consume power to be able to function. According to the World Bank, the higher the consumption of electricity, the more productivity can be experienced in the economy.

(2) **Air Transport Infrastructure Quality-ATIQ** - Which proxies Air transport passengers carried. Air passengers carried include both domestic and international aircraft passengers of air carriers registered in the country. The air transport industry is a vital engine of global socio-economic growth. It is of vital importance for economic development, creating direct and indirect employment, supporting tourism and local businesses, and stimulating foreign investment and international trade.

Justification : Air transport is a vital part of transport infrastructure in any country as it the quickest means to connect a country to others. Ability to efficiently transport people and goods by air is a major requirement in international trade and affects the foreign investment potentials.

(3) **Seaport Infrastructure Quality-SIQ** - Which proxies Quality of port infrastructure. The Quality of Port Infrastructure measures business executives' perception of their country's port facilities. Effective port facilities enable entrepreneurs to get their goods to market in a secure and timely manner.

Justification : Most goods in international trade are transported by sea freight, it gives an overall impression of that waterway connectivity of a country influences the attractiveness for foreign firms since they are able to transport their goods cheaply via waterways.

(4) **Railroad Infrastructure Quality-RIQ** - Which proxies Rail lines (total route-km). The railway transport industry a vital engine of global socio-economic growth. It is of vital importance for economic development, creating direct and indirect employment, supporting tourism and local businesses.

Justification: Rail transport is essential in the industrialization process of a country as it provides easy transportation of people, goods and raw-materials at a cheaper rate.

(5) **Mobile Phone Subscribers-MPS** - Which proxies Mobile cellular subscriptions. Mobile communications have a particularly important impact in rural areas. The mobility, ease of use, flexible deployment, and relatively low and declining roll-out costs of wireless technologies enable them to reach rural populations with low levels of income and literacy.

Justification : In case of market-seeking FDI which is common in Nigeria because of its population, the target group of domestic consumers can be reached easier when the people in such a group generally have Mobile Phone access. Companies can contact clients much easier by calls and text messages rather than going to meet them face to face. This makes this variable very important.

Specification of empirical model

The specification of the models involve the determination of the dependent and independent variables that will be included in the model. It expresses the mathematical relationship that exists between the dependent and the independent or explanatory variables. Our study adopts variables related to the infrastructure sectors. The relationship between these variables and Foreign Direct Investment can be represented functionally as:

$$FDI = f(PIQ, ATIQ, SIQ, RIQ, MPS).$$

In economics, we are often interested in how a percentage change in x (explanatory) affects the y (dependent). This called elasticity. We can estimate elasticity by using a log-log model. The above equation is represented in logarithmic form to enable us standardize all the values and interpret the variables' coefficients as elasticity:

$$\ln FDI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln PIQ + \beta_2 \ln ATIQ + \beta_3 \ln SIQ + \beta_4 \ln RIQ + \beta_5 \ln MPS + \varepsilon$$

Where

B_0 = constant term

β_{1-5} = the coefficients of the variables

ε =the error term

This research will adopt the multiple linear regression analysis. The choice of the appropriate technique in every research depends on the research problem as well as the study objectives. The second method of data analysis to be adopted for this study will be the **multiple linear regression technique** using the Ordinary Least Squares, (OLS). In regression analysis, the **Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Method** is widely used under the assumption that the OLS gives desirable properties of **Best Linear Unbiased Estimate (BLUE)**. This property has made OLS the most popular method of regression analysis. Therefore our study will utilize econometric technique of the ordinary least squares (OLS) model to determine the effect of infrastructure towards attracting Foreign Direct Investment in Nigeria.

Theoretical justification of model

According to the research conceptual framework based on the Eclectic Paradigm or Ownership, Location and Internalization (OLI) Model, we identify that there must be a certain level of Location advantage before a foreign company can decide to move its operations to another country. These location advantages include availability of key infrastructure that support international trade such as Transport, Power and Telecommunications infrastructure. This forms the background of our regression model with tests the effect of the interaction between these infrastructure indicators and foreign direct investment.

Priori Hypothesis

This shows whether each independent variable in the equation is consistent with the postulations of economic theory. That is, if the sign and size of the parameters of economic relationships follows the expectation of the economic theory. This must be based on the theoretical framework of the research matter. For this research study, the adopted trade theories suggests some relationships or effects of some of the variables on economic growth; These effect-relationships are ordinarily referred to as a priori hypothesis.

For the selected model, Economic postulations suggest that increase in the infrastructure levels will bring about increase in inflow Foreign Direct Investment. The expected signs of regression coefficients in the equation are: $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5 > 0$.

Table .1 : A Priori Hypothesis Table

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Expected Sign
PIQ	FDI	POSITIVE (+)
ATIQ	FDI	POSITIVE (+)
SIQ	FDI	POSITIVE (+)
RIQ	FDI	POSITIVE (+)
MPS	FDI	POSITIVE (+)

If estimates of the parameters of the model turn-up with magnitudes and signs (number) not in conformity with the adopted theories, they should be rejected unless there is a good reason or explanation to believe that due to peculiar instance(s) the theories would not hold.

Reliability Tests

Reliability Tests for evaluation of the model consists of deciding whether the estimated coefficients are theoretically meaningful and statistically satisfactory. For this study, there is need for all results to satisfy both statistical criteria (First order test) and econometric criteria (Second order test).

Statistical Criteria - This aims at the evaluation of the statistical reliability of the estimated parameters of the model. In this case, F-statistic, t-statistic, Coefficient of determination (R^2) and Adjusted R^2 are used.

The Coefficient of Determination (R^2)/Adjusted R^2 - The square of the coefficient of determination (R^2) or the measure of goodness of fit is used to judge the explanatory power of the explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The R^2 denotes the percentage of variations in the dependent variable accounted for by the variations in the independent variables. Thus, the higher the R^2 , the more the model is able to explain the changes in independent variable. Hence, the better the regression based on ordinary least square (OLS) techniques and this is why the R^2 is called the coefficient of determination as it shows the amount of variation in the dependent variable explained by explanatory variables. However, if R^2 equals one, it implies that there is 100% explanation of the variation in the dependent variable by the independent variable and this indicates a perfect fit of regression line. While where R^2 equals zero, it indicates that the explanatory variables could not explain any of the changes in the dependent variable. Therefore, the higher and closer the R^2 is to 1, the better the model fits the data.

The F-test - F test is used to explain the significance or fitness of the regression model being used are using. The F-test indicates whether the linear regression model provides a good fit for the independent variables. A significant F value indicates a linear relationship between Y and at least one of the X 's. The F-test for overall significance has the following two hypotheses:

If the P value for the F-test of overall significance test is less than assumed significance level(0.05 or 5%), we can reject the null-hypothesis and conclude that the model provides a better fit than the intercept-only model.

The t-statistic - This is used to determine the reliability/statistical significance of each variable's coefficient. Here, the absolute t-value of each coefficient is compared with 1.96 and if greater than 1.96, such variable possessing the coefficient is accepted as statistically significant and fit to be used for inferences and possibly for forecasting.

Econometric Criteria - This aims at investigating whether the assumptions of the econometric method employed are satisfied or not in any particular case. They determine the reliability of the statistical criteria and also establish whether the estimates have desirable properties of unbiasedness and consistency.

Breusch–Pagan test - This test is used to test for heteroskedasticity. One of the assumptions made about residuals/errors in OLS regression is that the errors have the same but unknown variance. This is known as constant variance or homoscedasticity. When this assumption is violated, the problem is known as

heteroscedasticity.” Homoscedasticity in regression is an important assumption; if the assumption is violated, you won’t be able to use regression analysis. If the p-value is 0.05 or smaller, then the null hypothesis is rejected and there is significant evidence the there is heteroskedasticity.

Durbin-Watson test for autocorrelation - Durbin-Watson’s “d” tests the null hypothesis that the residuals are not linearly auto-correlated. While “d” can assume values between 0 and 4, values around 2 indicate no autocorrelation. As a rule of thumb values of $1.5 < d < 2.5$ show that there is no auto-correlation in the data. The above tests are generally aimed at ascertaining that the regression model is the best linear unbiased estimator (BLUE) as described by the Gauss-Markov theorem.

Interpretation of Results

To examine the effect relationship of the chosen independent variables on Foreign Direct Investment (dependent variable), the regression analysis is inevitable. Using the E-Views 10 package, the parameter estimates that measure the effect of the explanatory variables on the dependent variable in both models were generated. The regression estimates are reported below:

Table 2: Summary of Regression Results

Dependent Variable : FDI				
Variable	Coefficient	Std.Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Constant	38.1549	9.6391	3.9583	0.0415
MPS	0.2812	0.0758	3.7085	0.0017
ATIQ	- 0.2730	0.2624	- 1.0404	0.3127
RIQ	- 14.3043	6.8723	- 2.0814	0.0869
SIQ	0.2249	0.1470	1.5298	0.0445
PIQ	- 0.0049	0.0099	0.4919	0.0629

Model: $FDI = 38.1549 + 0.2812 * MPS - 0.273 * ATIQ - 4.3043 * RIQ + 0.2249 * SIQ - 0.0049 * PIQ$

R-Squared = 0.8734	Adjusted R-Squared = 0.846
F-Statistic = 23.4666	Residual Std. Error Stat = 0.4017

Diagnostic Tests

Breusch-Pagan Test = 1.4066
Durbin-Watson Stat = 2.1131

Model Evaluation :

The Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination (R²) from the result is 87.34%. This implies that 87.34% of the total variation in FDI inflow is explained by the variables of the model. In essence, this shows that the explanatory power of the variables in the model is very high.

Adjusted R²

The adjusted R² supports the claim of the R² with a value of 84.60% indicating that 84.60% of the total variation in FDI inflow is explained or caused by the independent variables in the model.

The T-test

Here, we compare the calculated or estimated t-statistic with the critical t (usually assumed to be 1.96). H0: The variable has no significant effect on FDI. H1: The variable has significant effect on FDI. The results are shown below:

Table 3: The Results of the T-test

VARIABLES	T-Calculated	Critical Value	Conclusion
MPS	3.7085	± 1.96	Reject H ₀
ATIQ	-1.0404	± 1.96	Accept H ₀
RIQ	-2.0814	± 1.96	Reject H ₀
SIQ	1.5298	± 1.96	Accept H ₀
PIQ	0.4919	± 1.96	Accept H ₀

From the table 5.2, MPS and RIQ have significant relationship with FDI in Nigeria. In other words, they have significant influence on FDI whereas the ATIQ, SIQ and PIQ are statistically non-significant. As such they does not significantly affect FDI.

The Durbin-Watson Statistic

In testing for autocorrelation in the model, the Durbin-Watson statistic was used. From the regression result, the Durbin-Watson statistic is 2.11. This implies that there is a level autocorrelation since d^* is within the rule of thumb range of [1.5 to 2.5]. Thus eliminating the existence of autocorrelation.

Breusch–Pagan Heteroskedasticity Test

The Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity delivered a result of 1.4066 which is out of the rule of thumb range of ($p < 0.05$) thus heteroskedasticity is not assumed.

Analysis of Results

According to the results two (2) out of five (5) independent variables have positive and also significant influence on FDI. Mobile Phone Subscribers - MPS (0.2812) and Seaport Infrastructure Quality - SIQ (0.2249) both turned out positive and significant. We shall now analyze these results in detail to understand why they are so in the situation of Nigeria.

Mobile Phone Subscribers (MPS) and FDI - According to our test result Mobile Phone Subscribers, which serves as a proxy for the communication infrastructure in Nigeria, has a positive relationship with FDI coming into the country. Our result shows that a 1% increase in Mobile Phone subscribers will result in 0.28% increase in FDI coming into Nigeria. This is reasonable when considering the fact that Nigerian economy has shifted more towards information technology based services since the advent of GSM Technology in 2001.

Figure 4 FDI to MPS Trend

Source : Authors Own Computation/WorldBank

An article by the Economic Times in 2018 seems to support the hypothesis that telecommunications infrastructure is important to investors for attracting foreign investment. The advent of GSM Technology ushered in the arrival of Chinese Communication Giants Huawei and ZTE into the Nigerian economy. The growing number of Mobile phone subscribers has made Nigeria the biggest market in Africa in terms of Mobile phone users and this factor continues to attract international IT brands into Nigeria as there are now 10 private GSM service providers in Nigeria.

Air Transport Infrastructure (ATIQ) and FDI - According to our test result Air Transport Infrastructure, which is proxied by the Air Transport Passengers Carried in Nigeria, has a negative relationship with FDI coming into the country. Our result shows that a 1% increase in Air Transport Passengers Carried will result in 0.273% decrease in FDI coming into Nigeria. This is probably a reflection of the fact that the Nigerian aviation sector suffers from poor reputation for operational efficiency and safety.

Figure 5 FDI to ATIQ Trend

Source : Authors Own Computation/WorldBank

Issues faced by the aviation sector include absence of a coherent air transport policy, bad management, decaying facilities, loose security, closure of airports etc. This situation translates to the situation whereby there are not enough airlines to serve the 200 Million Nigerian who need it and as such foreign investors will be discouraged because they will have doubts about the ease and safety of transporting around the country.

Rail Infrastructure (RIQ) and FDI - According to our test result Rail Infrastructure, which is proxied by the Rail lines (total route-km) in Nigeria, has a negative relationship with FDI coming into the country. Our result shows that a 1% increase in Rail lines (total route-km) will result in 14.3% decrease in FDI coming into Nigeria. Nigeria has one of the most extensive national rail networks in Africa, second only to South Africa in length yet despite Nigeria’s potentially significant demand for rail, traffic volumes have all but collapsed—much more so than in many other African countries. Nigeria’s large population and economy create substantial demand for intercity passenger traffic as well as freight movements.

Figure 6 FDI to RIQ Trend

Source : Authors Own Computation/WorldBank

However, due to deficient performance and erratic service, traffic volumes have been on a long-term decline from 3 million tonnes in 1960 to 15,000 tonnes in 2017. Similarly, passenger traffic has declined from 2.3 million to 500,000 passengers per year over the same period—equivalent to about 25 buses per day. Knowing the role of rail transport in conveying goods and passenger and its essential role in economic activities it is not a surprise that there is a negative relationship between Rail infrastructure and FDI in Nigeria.

Seaport Infrastructure (SIQ) and FDI - According to our test result Rail Infrastructure, which is proxied by the Quality of port infrastructure in Nigeria, has a positive relationship with FDI coming into the country. Our result shows that a 1% increase in Quality of port infrastructure in Nigeria will result in 0.2249% increase in

FDI coming into Nigeria. Even though Nigerias port infrastructure still needs a lot of improvement, yet due to the size of Nigeria in terms of market size and proximity to the Atlantic ocean the sea ports in Nigeria serves as a hub for the whole West African region.

Figure 7 FDI to SIQ Trend

Source : Authors Own Computation/WorldBank

This has led to the attraction of investment in manufacturing clusters around the port locations such as Lekki Free Trade Zone, Ogun Guangdong Free trade zone and the on going Dangote Petrochemical Refinery. New Ports are also being opened along the coast lines of Nigeria due to the influx of foreign investment in manufacturing which will require these infrastructure. Considering these points we can understand why there is a positive relationship between Port Infrastructure and FDI in Nigeria.

Power Infrastructure (PIQ) and FDI - According to our test result Power Infrastructure, which is proxied by the Electric Power Consumption (Kwh per capita) in Nigeria, has a negative relationship with FDI coming into the country. Our result shows that a 1% increase in Electric Power Consumption (Kwh per capita)) will result in 0.0049% decrease in FDI coming into Nigeria. The country has achieved relatively high rates of electrification, particularly in urban areas, and access is expanding rapidly. Yet, despite high levels of electrification, Nigeria’s power sector has struggled to provide an adequate supply of reliable power. Power supply difficulties cripple the agricultural, industrial and mining sectors and impede the Nigeria's ongoing economic development.

Figure 8 FDI to PIQ Trend

Source : Authors Own Computation/WorldBank

The energy supply crisis is complex, stems from a variety of issues and has been ongoing for decades. Most Nigerian businesses and households that can afford to do so run one or more diesel-fueled generators to supplement the intermittent supply. These challenges will obviously not encourage foreign investors to set up factories and production units in Nigeria due to the cost implication. Ultimately we can understand why there is a negative relationship between FDI and Power Infrastructure.

Summary of Results

This research focused on the impact of Infrastructure on FDI in Nigeria. The research applied the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique to determine the effect of Infrastructure component variables of FDI in Nigeria. This was ascertained using the multiple regression technique with the E-Views Econometric Software.

Specifically, we found the following:

Our result shows that a 1% increase in Mobile Phone subscribers will result in 0.28% increase in FDI coming into Nigeria.

A 1% increase in Air Transport Passengers Carried will result in 0.273% decrease in FDI coming into Nigeria

A 1% increase in Rail lines (total route-km) will result in 14.3% decrease in FDI coming into Nigeria.

A 1% increase in Quality of port infrastructure in Nigeria will result in 0.2249% increase in FDI coming into Nigeria.

A 1% increase in Electric Power Consumption (Kwh per capita)) will result in 0.0049% decrease in FDI coming into Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study's primary objective is to empirically investigate the impacts of infrastructure on foreign direct investment inflow to Nigeria from 1996 to 2018. Specifically, it seeks to determine if there exists a long run

relationship between infrastructure and FDI in Nigeria or if these two macroeconomic variables converge in the long run. The study's tried to empirically answer the questions concerning how transport, power and communications infrastructure have impacted on FDI in Nigeria. The Eclectic Paradigm formed the theoretical background of this research with emphasis on the Location advantage of the OLI framework which pinpoints the role of infrastructure in attracting FDI.

Infrastructure indices from the Transport, Communication and Powers sub-sectors were analyzed in a multiple linear regression using the OLS method. The results revealed that 2 out of the 5 variables tested exhibited a positive relationship to FDI. A close analysis of the results generally highlight the fact that Nigeria though a big market and rich in resources is still lagging behind its peers in terms of infrastructure and this has made it difficult for foreign investors to come into the country to invest as expected.

Power Infrastructure and Rail infrastructure in particular showed poor results and considering the role of these two sub-sectors in the growth of any economy it becomes imperative that they must be resuscitated urgently to ensure that Nigeria can gain more inflow of Foreign Direct Investment. The Power infrastructure has performed poorly because of inadequate power generation, transmission and distribution systems across the country. Power infrastructure is probably the most important of all because almost all economic activities require electricity to function especially in the manufacturing sector.

Likewise the Rail infrastructure which performed poorly according to our test because although Nigeria has a reasonably extensive rail network yet they are basically moribund because there are very few functioning coaches and train stations to convey goods and passengers across the country. Rail transportation reduces costs of transportation greatly and as a result cuts cost of doing business. There is need for the urgent revival of the rail infrastructure in Nigeria.

We would like to recommend the following in the light of the insight gained from this study:

- 1) Drawing from the above we suggest that the on going power sector reforms currently being embarked on should be carried out to its logical conclusion in order to permanently settle the issue of power that has been a major bane of Nigeria's development. The significant impact electricity has in attracting FDI to Nigeria in the long run shows that the Nigerian government and the private sector should gear efforts towards resuscitating the ailing power sector, standardizing it and devising others means of generating alternative power supply, such as the adoption of other sources of power such as Solar, Wind and Coal into its energy mix, so as to realize the goal of becoming one of the leading twenty economies in the world by the year 2050.
- 2) Recent emphasis on revitalizing the ailing railway infrastructure across Nigeria must be encouraged. Recently Nigerian government has made efforts to revive rail infrastructure through cooperation with the Chinese government on various rail projects across the country. It is imperative that these projects must be executed successfully and spread evenly around the country to boost transport network, cut costs and facilitate ease of trade activities. The rail lines must also be connected to critical port facilities to enable easy and efficient movement of goods from the sea ports into the various cities across the country.

3) The Air transport or aviation sector needs major investment and restructuring dilapidated and worn out air infrastructure must urgently be renovated and replaced as the case may require. Air transport is one of the cheapest and quickest means of transportation and it is essential that Nigeria has an efficient and reliable aviation sector. Airports must be built to international standard and all safety instruments must be installed in order to attract passenger flight traffic from more airlines across the world. Policies to reduce cost of operations such as “the open skies” policy of 2017 should be encouraged as it would attract more foreign airlines to enter the Nigerian aviation market

4) Nigeria has been doing very well in terms of mobile phone technology and the resulting subscriptions. Since the technology was fully introduced in 2001, Nigeria has shot to the top in terms of mobile subscriptions in Africa. However, to fully maximize the gains from the technology of mobile phones then more has to be done to achieve deeper mobile internet penetration and boost electronic financial services which in turn makes business operations easier and more efficient. Rural dwellers must be sensitized on the benefits of mobile phone usage in their daily personal and business activities.

5) Port facilities across Nigeria needs to be upgraded with modern state of the art equipment to ensure timely clearing and processing of goods during import and export. Nigeria has faced competition from nearby countries Benin Republic, Togo and Ghana due to the cost of usage, port port facilities and processing time experienced in Nigerian ports. It is therefore of high priority that Nigeria must improve on these deficiencies and then they can even attract more port traffic. Also more modern seaports have to be constructed across the coastal lines of the country to further maximize the benefits of location and attract further foreign direct investment. As of today the Lagos seaports remain the main functional ports in Nigeria, it is imperative that ports in Calabar, Warri ,Port Harcourt and Onitsha must be upgraded and made fully functional to help decongest Lagos seaports and make port operations more convenient and efficient.

6) The Nigerian Government should also set up an agency or institution that is totally responsible for regular review and assessment of the situation of Infrastructure across the country . Nigeria has historically been guilty of poor maintainance culture and this has lead to many of the existing infrastructure not being well maintained, renovated or upgraded. So the government must ensure that there is an agency that is responsible for this task.

7) The Nigerian government should rather ensure that the private sector has sufficient incentives to invest in infrastructure development. To this end, the government needs to develop an efficient institutional framework and further improvements are also required in a number of areas to create a conducive environment. It is mandatory that strict regulations which do not support and encourage the private sector foreign investment should be removed. This is important because government cannot fund all infrastructure projects due to it's limited capabilities recently, as such the most efficient and cost saving alternative is to open the doors to private investment to bridge the funding gap. However, the regulatory framework must be suitable for investors to have confidence to enter and invest in the economy.

8) Ultimately it is worthwhile for the Nigerian government to setup institutions of learning where experts in infrastructure development can be educated and trained. This will ensure that Nigeria in future will not depend

on experts from foreign countries to develop and maintain their infrastructure but rather Nigerian experts can manage this task and even render the same services to neighboring countries around the West African region.

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